

Orchestra Course Outcomes in Terms of Values Education

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Abstract—Music education aims to bring up individuals most appropriately and to advanced levels as a balanced whole physically, cognitively, affectively, and kinesthetically while making a major contribution to the physical and spiritual development of the individual. The most crucial aim of music education, an influential education medium per se, is to make music be loved; yet, among its educational aims are concepts such as affinity, friendship, goodness, philanthropy, responsibility, and respect all extremely crucial bringing up individuals as a balanced whole. One of the most essential assets of the music education is the training of making music together, solidifying musical knowledge and enabling the acquisition of cooperation. This habit requires internalization of values like responsibility, patience, cooperativeness, respect, self-control, friendship, and fairness. If musicians lack these values, the ensemble will become after some certain time a cacophony. In this qualitative research, the attitudes of music teacher candidates in orchestra/chamber music classes will be examined in terms of values.

Keywords—Education, music, orchestra/chamber music, values.

I. INTRODUCTION

VALUES are the human specific entities that make human beings human and differentiate them from other animates; in other words all the human activities become humanistic activities only if they are conducted so as to fit their purpose [1]. Values can be defined as the beliefs acquired in line with the behaviors embraced by individuals' or groups' preferences [2].

The existence of a well-organized values education process is crucial on the path of self-actualization, socialization, and happiness. "The education process that enables individuals' moral, spiritual, and value existence and improvement results through understanding emotions, feelings, maintaining interpersonal communication, and social skills due to the presence of some certain feelings, beliefs, and attitudes" [3]. The internalization and assimilation of values is only possible by

Human beings think and act based on their values and standards of judgment. Although the fundamentals for the development of an individual's value system are in the family

life, school life constituting an essential part of one's social life has a great importance in this development.

As a fact, schools teach and discipline students according to the values clearly stated or implied in the school curriculum [4]. Throughout educational processes many aspects of teaching values have been demonstrated in the implementation of courses and values in education has found its way into curriculum. Within the various fields of social sciences, in many of the courses values are taught at the primary and secondary levels (Social Studies, Life Science, Turkish, Literature, Sociology, Citizenship and Democracy, Music etc.) and established schools rules contribute to the moral development of children and leave a positive mark their character. Many studies on teaching values in the academic fields seem to focus on these courses taught within the curriculum.

Music is an aesthetic single process describing for a particular purpose and using a particular method the feelings, thoughts, designs and impressions. Combined with sound, music describes a particular perception of beauty [5]. Although the most important aim of music education, an effective means of education per se, is to make music be loved, among its instructional aims are concepts such as inspiring the sense of beauty in the human beings, love, friendship, kindness, helpfulness, responsibility, and respect all of them are extremely important for bringing up a balanced individual [6].

Music is a discipline that allows cooperating, sharing, creating together, having mutual emotions, and living in harmony and solidarity within a society. Although there is no certain evidence about the emergence of music presently, views about the use of music as a means of communication and later of socializing in primitive societies dominate. As stated by Plato "aesthetic education has an impact on moral education". Children loving music will also love people, society, life, and acquire a unique mental power and richness [7].

Eskioğlu concluded in one of his studies that music education improves not only a child's physical abilities but also others along with music; namely besides the individual contribution of music and music education, they bond a society and improving its members moral values [7]. Individuals acquire not only some music related behaviors but also others related to different disciplines via music. Values education is one of those disciplines. Music education comes to the fore for making values education easier and more helpful in obtaining the expected gains from values education and enables these to become a part of their life. Music is one

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of the cultural entities providing the development of a common cultural product. "Thus, music education can include opportunities that contribute positively to values education because of the nature of music and music education. Hereby, the underlying notion behind is the ability of music to diffuse effectively and quickly into mans' soul as a communicative device. Considered out of a technical perspective, increase in the heartbeat and blood pressure caused by music with the fast rhythm or national songs are among the many examples that can be provided. Music is among the most effective cultural entities, enabling masses share mutual feelings and mold a society" [8]. Thus, significant benefits can be achieved with music education in teaching values.

There are various samples of music education and values education in teaching the values through lyrics. Within the scope of general music education, via the messages in children songs taught in elementary school textbooks both intended development in musicality and cognitive abilities are realized that contribute to psychosocial development of children. Moreover, besides individual musical practices, making music together leads people to accompany one another and cooperate. While performing sometimes the same and at other times different tasks, they all have to keep up with the beat. Music is a discipline that enables cooperation, sharing, mutual production, feeling the same emotions, and living in harmony and unity within a society. Although there is no certain data regarding the emergence of music, views about music as first as a tool of communication and later of socialization for primitive societies dominate. Therefore, the nature of playing together pushes people into a democratic environment.

There are different groups of instruments in orchestra/chamber music. The chief of a group is responsible for each instrument group, the concertmaster for all instrument groups, and the conductor responsible that all musical groups are within a musical balance. Orchestra/chamber music has to play differing themes to give the impression of a single music within a balanced integrity. For example, if there is excessive or insufficient rotundity, the musical production may shift away from the ideal musical character. Therefore, a theme and the musicians playing that theme in the forefront have to go to the background when necessary. Therefore all musicians and group of instruments must listen to each other. Each group of musical instrument has a different musical character and unifying all differentiations leads to the emergence of captivating music. The combination of these differences leads to harmony and reflects at the same the essence of democratic life [9].

Making music together is one of the important aspects of professional, general and amateur music education and is important as it enables learning, practicing, and consolidating values such as responsibility, patience, solidarity, sensitivity, diligence, discipline, cooperation, respect, love, charity, fairness, being democratic, being peacefulness, tolerance, humility, empathy, trust, and confidence.

The aim of the present study is to determine which values such as fairness, love, respect, patience, responsibility, diligence, solidarity, etc. are acquired by the students via the

orchestra/chamber music and chamber music courses lectured at the music education departments of universities. Considering that there are no postgraduate studies about values education and music education at national level, [10], [11] the present study will make a significant contribution the field of study.

II. METHOD

In this study, investigating the acquisitions of orchestra/chamber music courses from values education perspective is a descriptive study conducted according to survey model. "A Survey model is a type of research that aims to describe a situation as it was in the past or is currently. The subject, individual, or object of research is being defined within their own conditions as they are. No effort is made to change or affect them. The entity to learn about is there and present. What counts is to 'observe' and 'define' them appropriately" [12].

A. Study Group

The study group of the present research consists of 104 undergraduate students enrolled in 3rd and 4th classes of music education departments of NEU Ahmet Keleşoğlu Faculty of Education and BU Necatibey Faculty of Education Music Education Department who have responded to the questionnaire voluntarily.

B. Data Collection Tool

In the research, survey method and review of the relevant literature were the data collection tools. Data obtained from the relevant literature has led to the creation of a questionnaire fit for the problem and the purpose of the research in line with the views of three lecturers teaching orchestra/chamber music courses. The values, 20 in total, have been determined in line with expert views and of the values in the syllabus of the Ministry of Education Fine Arts High School Turkish and Western Music Orchestra/chamber music Course. In the questionnaire, the participants were asked to choose from the values in the list [13].

C. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The quantitative data collected through questionnaires within the framework of the overall objectives and the main problem of the research has been analyzed using SPSS 17 package program and interpreted based on the frequencies and percentages.

III. FINDINGS

Following results have been obtained in the present study focusing on values acquired in orchestra/chamber music classed based on students views after data analysis.

According to the findings in Table I, in line with the views of the students taking orchestra/chamber music courses, among the mostly acquired values are discipline (74%), responsibility (73,1%), cooperation (71,2%), patience (71,2%), solidarity (69,2%), diligence (57,7%), self-efficacy(54,8%), and tolerance (51%). It is evident that the

students' views focus on values such as discipline, responsibility, cooperation, and patience. It can be stated that these values are important for both increasing the productivity of the orchestra/chamber music course and for the cognitive development of an individual.

TABLE I
 STUDENTS' VIEWS ON THE VALUES ACQUIRED MOST IN
 ORCHESTRA/CHAMBER MUSIC COURSES

Values	N	%
Discipline	77	74
Responsibility	76	73,1
Cooperation	74	71,2
Patience	74	71,2
Solidarity	72	69,2
Diligence	60	57,7
Self-efficacy	57	54,8
Tolerance	53	51
Total	104	100

Considering the values between 50% and 60% in Table I, 'diligence, self-esteem, tolerance' are also among the values necessitating cooperation in courses such as orchestra/chamber music.

TABLE II
 OTHER VALUES ACQUIRED VIA THE ORCHESTRA/CHAMBER MUSIC COURSES
 ACCORDING TO STUDENTS

Values	N	%
Sensitivity	49	47,1
Esthetic	48	46,2
Love	45	43,3
Empathy	42	40,4
Being Democratic	39	37,5
Trust	39	37,5
Philanthropy	37	35,6
Modesty	29	27,9
Fairness	23	22,1
Peace	15	14,1
Patriotism	11	10,6
TOTAL	104	100

According to Table II, the values associated less than 50% with the orchestra/chamber music courses are sensitivity (47,1%), esthetic (46,2%), love (43,3%), empathy (40,4%), being democratic (37,5%), trust (37,5%), philanthropy- (35,6%) modesty (27,9%) fairness (22,1%), peace (14,4%), and patriotism (10,6%). According to Table II, the percentages of the 'peace and patriotisms' are the lowest among the values under 50%.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The value 'discipline' emerges out with (74%) among the students taking orchestra/chamber music/chamber music courses. The value discipline represents the care and rigor for one's own studies. Orchestra/chamber music/chamber music courses, necessitates that the students are not only neat and careful for their own sake but also for the sake of his/her band members. Any musician forgetting the notes to play will fall

into disfavor by the band members. Many details such as arrival at the course, preparation, adjusting equipment such as music stand will have an impact on the musical performance. A student who does not have the right intonation or can cope up with the rhythm will be scolded by the other students in the band or orchestra/chamber music. These issues force the students to be more disciplined or in other words make them acquire the value of discipline.

As the students gain 'responsibility' like 'discipline' this is reflected with 73,1 %. Hence, 'responsibility' that can be defined as a tendency for owning ones actions, orchestra/chamber music courses reinforces the sense of responsibility in the students. In the orchestra/chamber music, besides the rules of the music, there are a lot of rules ranging from the seating arrangement to the duties assigned within the orchestra/chamber music. All of these rules are rules determined for a better music performance. For example, the maestro, concertmaster, group chief, those seated in the center and outside do all have different responsibilities. There cannot be a good music if these responsibilities are not conducted. Therefore, in the orchestra/chamber music courses the chief is the person who teaches besides music the rules as the leader of the orchestra/chamber music.

The students have chosen to 71, 2% percent 'cooperation' the value. The chamber music practices are collective music practices and due to their nature cooperation is unavoidable. The high percentage shown by the students implies that the opportunities to understand 'cooperation' and acquire have been provided by those lecturing orchestra/chamber music courses. However, at a significant degree (28,8%) students have expressed that they did not acquire the value of cooperation. Although the orchestra/chamber music/chamber music is a common area for making music, it is clear that this percentage is insufficient. Those responsible for the courses should be more careful in developing the sense of 'cooperation' in all the students and provide opportunities to cooperate during orchestra/chamber music/chamber music practices.

The percentage of the students who claim that they have acquired the values 'patience' in the orchestra/chamber music/chamber music classes is 71,2%. 'patience' is an important concept on the road to success. In order to perform a good music, the musician has to be patient. A music performance made of different components has to wave all the components into a single piece patiently. Considering orchestra/chamber music/chamber environments, musicians are united for a common purpose come to the mind. These musicians or students of music know that they achieve their aims after a long time. Hence, 'patience' is a value that comes to the fore while making music together. At the same time 'patience' is also associated with enduring the mistakes made during common music performance or those who do not perform their responsibilities. With all these different considerations, 'patience' has a clear and a significant contribution to the students in orchestra/chamber music/chamber music environments. The lecturers can be more effective in enabling the students to acquire 'patience'.

Another value acquired by the individuals in a social sense is 'corporation'. The value of 'corporation' accepted at 69,2% by the students shows that they have developed an awareness for helping each other while performing their duties in the orchestra/chamber music/chamber music classes. 'solidarity', 'cooperation' could be considered as values to help out others in the workplace if needed. Although unity and team spirit are among the important factors for success in people who came together for a common musical cause, it is also of prime importance for the emerging musicality of the common music product. Musical groups consisting of members knowing each other well and who complete each other are considered to be more successful.

Among the values necessary for making music together is 'diligence'. Above 50% of participating students have expressed that they have gained 'diligence' in the orchestra/chamber music/chamber music courses at 57,7%. The process in the orchestra/chamber music can be compared to a factory. In order to produce high quality products all units have to work in synchrony and harmony. Any unit that cannot perform its task will have a negative impact on production. The musician who cannot play their part efficiently will destroy the harmony. It is important that all members of the orchestra/chamber music come to rehearsals having practiced their part best. Those who have not coped up with the fidelities of their part will lead to prolonged rehearsal time and make these boring and unproductive. Therefore, diligence is among the important values in the members of the orchestra/chamber music. Although orchestra/chamber music/chamber music students have expressed at 57,7% that they have gained the value 'diligence', this percentage can be considered as low. The maestro has to emphasize to the members of the orchestra/chamber music, that music is an education for perfection and the harder they practice the more successful they will be.

The percentage of the students who believe that they have acquired 'self-esteem' in the Orchestra/chamber music/chamber music classes is 54,8%. Self-efficacy is the perception of an individual to be of value [14]. Lack of self-esteem is a significant factor to effect musical performance. Introvert musicians in the orchestra/chamber music who cannot play their part in saturity will disturb the voice homogeneity of the orchestra/chamber music. Therefore, all those involved with performing arts must have positive self-efficacy believes.

Another value acquired more than the average is 'tolerance'. Considering the preparation stage of orchestra/chamber music, it emerges after long, disciplined rehearsals. Within this process, the members of the group have to show each other affection, respect, and tolerance is among the important values to be found in team spirit.

Orchestra/chamber music classes are among the most important lessons for the practice of music. There are some certain traditional rules and rituals conducted for centuries both in amateur and professional orchestra/chamber music. As highlighted in the present study, these rules and rituals are reflections of the values bonding a society. Therefore,

especially enabling the students to acquire the skill of making music together, will reinforce the acquisition of many skill that are vital for a social life within the natural environment of music.

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